

CAUSES OF THE TAIWAN PROBLEM AND ITS POSSIBLE NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES IN THE FUTURE

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Annotation: *In this article, the author examines the origins of the Taiwan problem and the reasons for the PRC's current pressure on Taiwan, as well as the political views of the United States on this interference. He gave his perspective on the interests that cause conflict in Taiwan. He described Taiwan's current position in the international arena. He spoke of the importance of the status quo and the reasons for the U.S. policy of containing China. He made suggestions for the future of Taiwan.*

Keywords: *status quo, Taiwan, U.S., People's Republic of China.*

The goal is to find a solution to the problems between the People's Republic of China and the government of Taiwan by examining the U.S.-Taiwan conflict, once a province of the Chinese state.

Method: *comparative analysis, synthesis, analogy, comparative synthesis.*

Conclusion: *As a result of the political pressure so far exerted by the United States government to protect the Taiwanese government from the influence of the People's Republic of China, the Taiwanese government now also exerts its influence.*

The outbreak of war almost all over the world, as well as the fact that Japan continued its fascist activities in China, as did its allies, and at the same time annexed Taiwan to its territory by Japan, anti-fascist forces, i.e., the USA, the USSR, the Great Patriotic War leads to the acceleration of anti-fascist movements in England, France, and other countries. This creates an anti-fascist coalition against Germany, Japan, and Italy.

By the end of World War II, China was divided on the political map of the world into two parts. Part of China was controlled by the Kuomintang (which was renamed the National Party and transformed into the ruling bourgeois-landlord party in 1927) and the remaining half of the territory was led by the Communist Party of China (CPC). The actions of the Communist

Party were supported by the people of the entire country through their anti-Japanese actions, which were supported by the Soviet Union, and the Kuomintang group was supported by the United States.

On the international scene after the end of World War II, the leading countries began to secede, at which time Taiwan was returned de jure and de facto to China, (Taiwan belonging to the Chinese people for many years, 1894) The territory occupied by Japan as a result of the Sino-Japanese War of 1895 was annexed by China in 1945 following Japan's defeat in World War II. Within a few years, the Taiwan issue escalated into a civil war unleashed by the Kuomintang in China, and foreign intervention in the war exacerbated the situation in the country. At that time, the Communist Party movement against the Japanese invasion of Chinese territory formed a national front against the Japanese invaders and fought against the aggression of the Japanese invaders; in fact, this movement was almost doomed to failure.

After the long-awaited victory over the Japanese invaders, everyone wanted the two parties to unite and form a strong Chinese state, but the Kuomintang, led by Zhang Kaishi, relied on U.S. support to build a peaceful, independent, prosperous democratic state for China. The Chinese people sought to break the "October 10 Agreement" signed between the two parties on the way to creating a new China, a situation that would lead to civil war throughout China.

As a result, the Chinese people led the People's Liberation War led by the Communist Party, which lasted more than three years, and the government of the People's Republic of China in Nanjing Province was overthrown by the fighters of the People's Liberation Movement. The fact that the Kuomintang was rejected by all peoples living in China also created ample opportunity for Communist Party supporters. By October 1, 1949, the founding of the People's Republic of China would be widely

proclaimed, paving the way for the long-awaited establishment of a legitimate and strong government. Some of the persecuted Kuomintang politico-military figures are about to leave. Taiwan, with the support of the then U.S. government, would establish a border post between the two sides of the Taiwan Strait.

As a result of the unification of bipolar China, many rights would be merged into provinces, but the U.S. government, supported by the Kuomintang government, would retain its influence over Taiwan despite the defeat of the Kuomintang.

Not only did the U.S. government support the Kuomintang in waging the Civil War, but it also failed to achieve its goal, even though it provided the Kuomintang with money and weapons to thwart the revolutionary work of the Chinese people. The U.S. government made this clear in a 1949 White Paper on U.S.-China relations published by the U.S. State Department.

U.S. Secretary of State Acheson's letter to President Truman says he was forced to acknowledge the situation. In the letter Acheson said: "Unfortunately, the terrible consequences of the civil war in China were not under the control of the United States government, but it is true." "Our country has taken no action to prevent it," he said. This is a product of China's internal forces; we tried, but we could not." sent a letter.

Despite the difficulties, the People's Republic of China was formed, and the United States government could have emerged from the civil war in China at that time, relying on its strong political capabilities, but was unable to do so. In addition, with the outbreak of the Korean War (after World War II there was also a political struggle between the United States and the Soviet state on Korean territory, on June 25, 1950, with the support of the Soviet state, North Korean troops launched a surprise attack. Their goal was to overthrow the South Korean government and reunify the country under the leadership of Kim Il-sung) The situation is further complicated by U.S. military intervention in the Chinese Taiwan Strait. On June 27, 1950, President Truman of the United States said in a statement, "I have ordered the Seventh Fleet to prevent any attack on Taiwan" . Thus, the U.S. 7th Fleet entered the Taiwan Strait. By December 1954, the United States had signed an agreement with the Taiwanese government. Under U.S. auspices, a "joint defense agreement" would be signed in the Taiwan Province of China. This misguided policy of the U.S. government to interfere in China's internal affairs would be a major cause of the protracted tensions in the Taiwan Strait. Thus, the Taiwan issue has become a major issue of intolerance between China and the United States.

Analyzing the above situation, we can understand the actions of the PRC in relation to Taiwan, historically Taiwan was one of the Chinese provinces, and the beginning of the civil war in the country led to the preservation of the state system by representatives of the Kuomintang. begin to interfere in the internal affairs of the country, supporting their efforts, and the defeat of the Kuomintang group draws the attention of the US government to the Taiwan Strait to gain influence over the formed government in China, and it succeeds in this. The gradual rise of the newly formed Chinese state and the cooling of relations with the Soviet government would lead to a softening of relations between the United States and China.

By December 1978, the United States government had adopted three important principles for establishing diplomatic relations with the Chinese government:

- Severing diplomatic relations with the government of Taiwan,
- Termination of the "joint defense treaty".
- Withdrawal of troops from Taiwan.

On January 1, 1979, Chinese and U.S. officials established diplomatic relations. A joint statement on the establishment of diplomatic relations between the People's Republic of China and the United States states: "The United States recognizes that the government of the People's Republic of China is the sole legitimate government of China. At the same time, the American people will maintain cultural, commercial and other informal ties with the people of Taiwan"; "The United States Government recognizes China's position that there is one China and Taiwan is part of China." Thus, Sino-American relations were somewhat normalized.

After the reunification of the territory of the divided Chinese state, citizens on both sides of the Taiwan Strait could work together to further strengthen and develop the new China. The government of Taiwan is not free from the problems it constantly struggles with, and as a solution to this problem, a reasonable solution can be found within the framework of the People's Republic of China.

Conclusion: At present, the Chinese government has always categorically opposed the supply and sale of any kind of weapons to Taiwan by any country, as well as the supply of weapons manufacturing equipment to Taiwan. All countries that have diplomatic relations with China should adhere to the principles of mutual respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, non-interference in each other's internal affairs and refrain from supplying weapons to Taiwan in any form and under any pretext,

otherwise their actions would be a violation of international norms, violation and interference in China's internal affairs.

Unfortunately, the Taiwan issue has remained a destabilizing factor in the Asia-Pacific region for many years. The implementation of the China-Taiwan unification will not only affect China's stability and development, but will also lay an excellent foundation for further strengthening China's relations of friendship and cooperation with other countries and ensuring peace and development in the Asia-Pacific region. In international affairs, the Chinese government has consistently pursued an independent and peace-loving foreign policy, adhering to five principles: "mutual respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, non-aggression, non-interference in each other's internal affairs, equality and reciprocity. followed. interests, peaceful coexistence, the rapid development of friendly relations with all countries of the world, will never violate the interests of other states, and will not interfere in the internal affairs of other states. For its part, the People's Republic of China calls on governments around the world not to compromise or harm China's interests, to recognize China's sovereignty without interfering in China's internal affairs, and to normalize relations with Taiwan.

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